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STUDY OF CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates clinical and epidemiological characteristics of acute intestinal infections in pregnant women. Despite available data, there is insufficient research on the etiology of acute intestinal infections (AII) in pregnant women. According to WHO recommendations, the term "acute intestinal infections" (AII) encompasses over 30 diseases, ranging from bacterial to viral and protozoal in etiology. The impact of contributing factors on structural changes and clinical manifestations remains inadequately studied, with limited coverage in both local and international scientific publications. The study revealed that opportunistic flora predominantly constitutes the etiological structure of acute intestinal infections (AII) in women aged 18 to 38 years. Despite the similarity in the etiological structure between pregnant and non-pregnant women, the course of AII differs. Pregnant women tend to experience the disease without a significant fever, unlike non-pregnant women. This difference may be attributed to the physiological changes during pregnancy, such as the release of corticosteroids by the placenta, which could modulate the immune response. Despite these differences, the spectrum of AII pathogens remains unchanged in both pregnant and non-pregnant women, indicating that clinical differences persist regardless of pregnancy status.

Keywords: acute intestinal infections, etiological factors, pregnant women

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ КЛИНИКО-ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ТЕЧЕНИЯ ОСТРЫХ КИШЕЧНЫХ ИНФЕКЦИЙ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлена информация об исследовании клинико-эпидемиологических особенностей острых кишечных инфекций у беременных. У беременных женщин факторы, влияющие на изменение этиологической структуры острых кишечных инфекций (ОКИ), а также особенности их клинических проявлений изучены недостаточно и недостаточно представлены в отечественных и зарубежных научных изданиях. В результате исследования установлено, что этиологическую структуру острых кишечных инфекций (ОКИ) у женщин в возрасте от 18 до 38 лет составляет преимущественно условно-патогенная флора. Несмотря на сходство этиологической структуры у беременных и небеременных, течение ОКИ различается. Беременные женщины, как правило, переносят заболевание без значительной лихорадки, в отличие от небеременных женщин. Эту разницу можно объяснить физиологическими изменениями во время беременности, такими как выделение кортикостероидов плацентой, которые могут модулировать иммунный ответ. Несмотря на эти различия, спектр возбудителей ОКИ остается неизменным как у беременных, так и у небеременных женщин, что указывает на сохранение клинических различий независимо от статуса беременности.

Ключевые слова: острые кишечные инфекции, этиологическая структура, беременные

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada homilador ayollarda o'tkir ichak infeksiyalarini klinik va epidemiologik xususiyatlarini o'rganish haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Homilador ayollarda, o'tkir ichak infeksiyalarining (O'II) etiologik tuzilishidagi o'zgarishlarga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar, shuningdek ularning klinik ko'rinishlarining xususiyatlari yetarlicha o'rganilmagan va mahalliy va xorijiy ilmiy nashrlarda kam taqdim etilgan. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, 18 yoshdan 38 yoshgacha bo'lgan ayollarda opportunistik flora asosan o'tkir ichak infeksiyalarining (OII) etiologiyasini tashkil qiladi. Homilador va homilador bo'lmagan ayollar o'rtasidagi etiologik tuzilishning o'xshashligiga qaramasdan, O'II kechishi farq qiladi. Homilador ayollar, homilador bo'lmagan ayollardan farqli o'laroq, sezilarli isitmasiz kasallikni boshdan kechirishadi. Bu farq homiladorlik davridagi fiziologik o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin, masalan, platsenta tomonidan kortikosteroidlar chiqarilishi, bu immunitet reaksiyasini modulyatsiya qilishi mumkin. Ushbu farqlarga qaramasdan, O'II patogenlarining spektri homilador va homilador bo'lmagan ayollarda o'zgarishsiz qolmoqda, bu klinik farqlar homiladorlik holatidan qat'iy nazar davom etishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'tkir ichak infeksiyalari, etiologik tuzilish, homilador ayollar

Relevance. Acute intestinal infections (AII) rank second globally among contagious diseases, following acute respiratory viral infections (ORVI) [1]. According to WHO recommendations, the term "acute intestinal infections" (AII) encompasses over 30 diseases, ranging from bacterial to viral and protozoal in etiology. The main symptom of AII is acute diarrhea, often accompanied by intoxication and, in severe cases, dehydration due to disruptions in gastrointestinal tract function caused by various contagious diseases within this polyetiological group. At the current stage, AII remains widespread [2, 27].

AII pathogens belong to diverse taxonomic groups, including bacteria, viruses, and protozoa. Among bacterial AII, *Shigella* species are most common, followed by *Salmonella* species, pathogenic strains of *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus* species, *Campylobacter* species, *Klebsiella* species, and others [3]. In recent years, a notable shift has occurred in the leading etiological agents of AII, with opportunistic bacteria and viruses gaining prominence [4,5]. Noroviruses and rotaviruses are the dominant viral pathogens causing AII [3, 28]. There are differences in the etiological structure of AII between children and adults. Viral AII accounts for approximately 60% of cases in children, while this proportion is much lower in adults [3]. According to WHO data, worldwide, approximately 275 million cases of diarrhea in children and adults are reported daily. Regardless of social status, nationality, race, gender, or age, people in almost all countries experience illness throughout the year, with a peak during the spring and summer months.

Acute intestinal infections pose a significant threat to public health globally, with diseases such as cholera, typhoid fever, botulism, salmonellosis, dysentery, and brucellosis being among the most dangerous. These diseases remain a leading cause of illness and death worldwide, resulting in approximately 1.5 to 2 million deaths annually, with two-thirds of these deaths occurring in children under 10 years old [10].

Shigellosis exhibits distinctive clinical features in pregnant women, including high fever above 38°C, which occurs five times more frequently in pregnant women than in non-pregnant women. Pregnant women with shigellosis often experience diarrhea with a mixture of mucus and blood, which is nearly twice as common as in non-pregnant patients. In most cases, fecal normalization occurs within the first 7-10 days of illness in pregnant women, compared to an average of 22 days or longer in non-pregnant women of reproductive age. However, systematic information on AII etiology and clinical presentation in pregnant women remains insufficient and requires further research attention.

Research Objective: The aim of this study is to investigate the clinical and epidemiological characteristics of acute intestinal infections (AII) in pregnant women of reproductive age and non-pregnant women.

Research Method and Materials: The research involved the diagnosis of acute intestinal infections (AII) in patients admitted to the infectious diseases hospital in the Samarkand region, aged between 18 and 38 years, totaling 76 individuals. The patients were divided into two groups: the main group comprised pregnant women, totaling 38 individuals, while the control group consisted of non-pregnant women with AII, also numbering 38. Examination materials included general blood, urine, and stool analyses, as well as bacteriological analysis of stool samples. Clinical, epidemiological, laboratory, and statistical methods were employed for data collection and retrospective analysis.

Research Discussion:

The study was conducted based on observations of patients admitted to the Samarkand Regional Clinical Hospital of Infectious Diseases. These patients were from both urban and rural areas within the districts of Samarkand city and Samarkand region districts.

Figure 1. Residential Address Distribution (%):

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of patients' residential addresses. Among the observed patients, 50.8% were from Samarkand city, while the remaining 49.2% were from various districts.

Incidence of Intestinal Diseases:

When analyzing the incidence of intestinal diseases caused by AII among our observed patients over the course of a year (Figure 2), the following trends were observed:

Figure 2. Seasonality (%).

Pregnant women sought medical attention for symptoms of gastrointestinal tract dysfunction on day 2-3 of illness (1.3 ± 0.98), while non-pregnant women sought help on day 2 (1.2 ± 0.48). There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of the frequency of detection of various AII pathogens. The maximum duration of AII symptoms in pregnant women was 7 days, while in non-pregnant women, it was 6 days.

In the main group, gastroenteritis was the most prevalent disease in 23 cases (60.52%), followed by enterocolitis in 11 cases (28.94%), gastroenterocolitis in 4 cases (10.52%), and enteritis in 1 case (0.38%). In the comparison group, gastroenteritis occurred in 20 cases (52.63%),

enterocolitis in 12 cases (31.57%), and gastroenterocolitis in 6 cases (15.7%). There was no statistically significant difference in intestinal damage syndromes between the groups.

Clinical manifestations of AII included diarrhea, vomiting, fever, and stomach pain in both groups. The average frequency of diarrhea in pregnant women with AII upon hospital admission was 5.6 ± 3.2 times a day, compared to 5.7 ± 4.9 times a day in non-pregnant women. The maximum duration of diarrhea was 7 days in pregnant women and 6 days in non-pregnant women. High frequency of diarrhea was observed in non-pregnant women on the 2nd day of illness.

Among non-pregnant women, 80% reported pain complaints, while among pregnant women, 28.3% reported pain complaints. Furthermore, 31.6% of patients in the main group were in labor during assessment, which complicated the evaluation of abdominal pain.

Fever was more commonly observed in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant women (83.3% vs. 36.7% respectively, $\chi^2=17.457$, $p<0.0001$). The duration of fever was 3 days in the main group and 5 days in the control group.

Vomiting occurred in 60.0% of pregnant women and 46.6% of non-pregnant women. The duration of vomiting did not exceed 3 days in both groups, with vomiting occurring more frequently in non-pregnant women only on the 2nd day of illness. The course of the disease was categorized based on severity: 29.6% of cases exhibited a severe form, 59.7% had a medium-severe form, and 10.7% had a mild form (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Severity of course (%).

Assessment of vital functions in both groups, including heart rate and blood pressure, showed no significant differences in indicators.

Stool analysis (coprogram) was conducted for 70% of patients in the main group and 66.6% of patients in the comparison group. Non-pregnant women were more likely to have erythrocytes detected in coprogram with symptoms of colitis compared to pregnant women (38.4% and 56.7%, respectively). However, no statistical difference was found in the number of leukocytes detected in both groups.

Bacteriological analysis for diagnosing AII was positive in 89.9% of pregnant women and 86.7% of non-pregnant women. Bacterial microflora was commonly observed in both groups, with opportunistic microflora (ShPF) predominating.

Conclusion: The study revealed that opportunistic flora predominantly constitutes the etiological structure of acute intestinal infections (AII) in women aged 18 to 38 years. Despite the similarity in the etiological structure between pregnant and non-pregnant women, the course of AII differs. Pregnant women tend to experience the disease without a significant fever, unlike non-pregnant women. This difference may be attributed to the physiological changes during pregnancy, such as the release of corticosteroids by the placenta, which could modulate the immune response. Despite these differences, the spectrum of AII pathogens remains unchanged in both pregnant and non-pregnant women, indicating that clinical differences persist regardless of pregnancy status.

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